

Using Knowledge Representation to achieve Reliable and trustworthy AI in Sensitive Infrastructure

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence (AI) has become increasingly integrated into various aspects of society, from healthcare and finance to law enforcement and hiring processes, and more recently sensitive infrastructure such as nuclear plants are trying to engage Artificial intelligence into aspect of safety. However, these systems are not immune to biases and ethical concerns. This paper explores the role of knowledge representation in addressing ethics and fairness in AI, examining how biased or incomplete representations can lead to unfair outcomes, unreliable decision making, and proposing strategies to mitigate these risks.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, bias in AI, knowledge representation, trustworthy AI, sensitive infrastructure, data bias, Explainable AI, algorithmic fairness.

1. INTRODUCTION

The world has been constantly evolving at a rapid pace, with many sectors have been implementing the use of Artificial intelligence to make it more efficient, either if it is the use in healthcare for making medical decisions, or for AI in the recruitment field to make screening process easier, more fair and faster, however the connivence that AI brings does not come at a cheap price, many consequences have been linked to AI some that can cause serious harm in some sectors(healthcare racial bias, recruits gender bias), such as bias(underrepresented data, biased data), algorithmic unfairness or unreliable decisions, which is one of the causes why some experts in sensitive infrastructure are hesitant to the use of AI in their field, as the consequences of biased or unreliable AI in such fields can be catastrophic.

Knowledge representation is a foundational element in AI, influencing how systems perceive, process, and act upon information. When the representation of knowledge is biased or misrepresented, the AI system can produce discriminatory or unreliable results/unreliable decision making. For example, if a dataset used for training a machine learning model contains racial, gender, or other forms of bias, the model's decisions will likely reflect those biases, or in case of sensitive infrastructure, underrepresented or inaccurate data could lead to catastrophic consequences. Similarly, incomplete or outdated knowledge structures can lead to incorrect or unfair interpretations of data.

2. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

2.1. Bias in Artificial intelligence

Artificial intelligence has been making several sectors easier and more accessible, and many of these sectors are affected by the bias caused by AI, some greater than other, for example healthcare is both benefited by AI and also been greatly affected by the bias it causes either by data or algorithm, the problem is in healthcare it is affected greatly by racial bias data that causes misdiagnosis or even consequences that could be fatal if the user fully relies on AI, that is why there is a necessity to identify the existence of bias either in the dataset or the algorithm and apply techniques or policies to eliminate it, this section discusses the different sources of bias in knowledge representation by examining common sources in bias for AI including biased dataset and flawed design choices, these sources can

affect the accuracy and fairness of AI systems that could lead to issues like racial bias, gender bias, discrimination and injustice.

Bias has been a major issue for AI, as a rising number of research and study has been dedicated to the subject, but very few developers address the issue, the bias is either caused by data due to the fact it comes from restricted demographic or lack of diversity, or the model itself can suffer from algorithmic bias, even some experts[1] refer the bias as lack of diversity among algorithm designers as the person who design the model or chooses data input, they can transfer their bias into the model, and a lack of training about the social and historical context of their work.

2.2. Statistical bias caused by unbalanced data

Overgeneralization bias

The bias in AI can induce major implications that range from fairness, equity and societal wellbeing. Whether the bias is reflected from data they learn from the algorithm biased decision-making process, the consequences remain the same across various domains such as healthcare, recruitment or finance. The bias AI can result in discriminatory actions and that can reinforce stereotypes. Bias in healthcare can result into dispersity towards underrepresented demographic groups, a study[2] showed that an algorithm widely used in the US public hospitals, to help facilitate identify the list of patients eligible for urgent kidney transplant, have been assigning dark skinned patients with higher eGFR which puts them at the bottom of the list, as by nature black patients have high creatinine levels in their blood, which makes their eGFR higher than different ethnic groups, as using race in such algorithms will cause racial bias and dispersity, an African American researcher[3] has used results from a DNA website to proof that she is only 48% African, in order to change her race in the algorithm, which resulted into receiving a lower eGFR that helped to qualify faster for a kidney transplant, and such bias can result into fatal results.

Stereotype bias

Gender bias is one of the most known form of stereotype bias, as it is known to perpetuate inequality by favouring certain individuals over others solely based on gender, such bias leads to discriminatory outcome, especially in the area of recruitment, addressing such bias is very important as it requires careful consideration when it comes to data processing phase, as some researchers[4] propose incorporation of statisticians in the AI development to limit any issues of gender bias.

Amazon[5] has been infamous for using an algorithm for their recruitment process, that was trained on mostly data that is underrepresented and mostly included only men, which gave clear bias to men, as the algorithm has eliminated resumes that included the term "woman".

Stereotype bias occurs when an algorithm makes assumptions or judgements about individuals based on gender stereotypes, rather than applying a process that only evaluates skills and experience, such an issue encourages harmful stereotypes that creates barriers to the efforts of gender diversity.

The bias is induced by AI in different sectors, can be damaging in so many different aspect, so if such issues are not solved and more concrete solutions were used, the results AI bias can cause in sensitive infrastructures can be catastrophic, for example if used for predictive maintenance such as in power plants, this induced bias due to biased data or flawed algorithmic bias may unreliably predict maintenance needs or false equipment failures, this can result in unnecessary maintenance scheduling, increase of downtime and possible catastrophic failures in such infrastructure.

Also the process of decision making that are used in emergency response systems can have profound effects on the resilience and effectiveness of the infrastructure, the use of a potentially biased algorithm, it can cause unequal resource allocation, delayed response time, risk of physical harm.

Even if the use of AI is still not integrated directly in sensitive infrastructure, bias induced by data can have extreme consequences on the reliability, safety and effectiveness of such infrastructure. It is important to address the issue of AI bias in all domains to ensure its reliability and trustworthiness before proceeding to employ it in sensitive infrastructure.

2.3. Algorithmic bias

Algorithmic bias is usually referred to as bias embedded in the design or implementation process of AI, however it is always most likely linked somehow to data, as if the algorithm uses biased[6] data it will repeatedly produce errors and biased decision that could be either unfair output or the wrong one and this can happen from multiple factors besides data. Algorithmic bias[7] has been described and defined in the healthcare sector, specifically ophthalmalgia care, where clear signs have shown signs of social injustice, based on geography within and between countries, also depending on ethnicity and social economic state.

Programming errors can also lead to algorithmic bias, where developers unintentionally embed biases into their systems. This often occurs when indicators, such as income or race, unjustly influence decision-making. For instance, facial recognition technologies in law enforcement struggle to accurately recognize Black faces, the algorithm has proved to have inbuilt racial bias, as these algorithms have been coded by white developers, this lack of diversity in developers can reflect in resulting extreme bias. Research from the MIT Media Lab[8] indicates that these biases arise from algorithms developed without accounting for diverse features,. This was highlighted when a person of colour was wrongfully arrested based solely on algorithmic identification, demonstrating the serious consequences of biased coding practices.

A similar issue arose with Google's image recognition algorithm, which faced criticism for misclassifying darker-skinned individuals as "gorillas"[9]. Investigations revealed that this bias resulted not from the dataset but from the feature selection process, which categorized images by gender rather than race. This oversight led Google to remove the term "gorilla" from its search results, underscoring the importance of addressing bias in AI technologies.

Feature selection bias pertains to the specific features AI algorithms use for decision-making. The selection or omission of certain features can lead to biased assumptions and unreliable outcomes. Biases often originate during data collection, which developers may not control. Sample selection[10] bias can create misleading correlations between features and target variables, ultimately undermining the performance and reliability of AI systems. Recognizing and mitigating these biases is essential for ensuring equitable functioning across diverse applications of AI technologies.

Another less common type of bias but equally harmful, is lack of diversity and gender equality of AI developers in a team[11], that can induce their own bias, such bias can be labelled as "Diversity Bias", this bias is rooted from the homogeneity of perspectives, background, ethnicity and experience of individuals taking part in the process of AI design, implementation and testing. This bias can either be called representation Bias or perspective bias.

As the developers unintentionally induce their own bias in the AI system, this lack of gender and social diversity might not seem important, however its consequences can be noticeable , as researchers believe the integrity of AI developers is critical to limit bias[12].

3. KNOWLEDGE REPRESENTATION WITHIN AI FRAMEWORK

3.1. Knowledge representation and artificial intelligence

Knowledge representation is a fundamental aspect of AI, focusing on how information is structured and organized to enable algorithms to understand and utilize it effectively. This process is essential for

creating AI systems capable of reasoning, learning, and making informed decisions, ultimately contributing to the development of more ethical, trustworthy, and reliable AI technologies.

Many research in AI has shown that the choice of proper terms, language and description has an effect on bias or user experience, researchers at standford [13] have expressed that most problems encountered in healthcare AI could be rooted from the fact that algorithms, are mostly not well documented in terms of explaining the AI system and its functionality, which leads to lack of transparency.

By ensuring that knowledge is represented in a transparent, coherent, and contextually relevant manner, we can enhance the AI's ability to interpret data accurately and fairly. This approach not only aids in minimizing biases but also fosters ethical and reliable AI systems. Ultimately, a robust framework for knowledge representation is essential for creating AI technologies that are both responsible and equitable, as it directly impacts how machines comprehend and engage with the world around them.

Several methods can be employed for knowledge representation in AI, each enhancing the system's capacity for reasoning and understanding information effectively. The following sections will detail these methods in depth.

Ontology based Representation

This method provides a formal framework for knowledge representation, by allowing for explicit modelling of concepts, relationships, and constraints. Developing ontologies that capture diverse perspectives and ensure inclusivity, AI systems can better account for the complexities of human knowledge and avoid reinforcing biases. Ontology based representation offers a lot of benefits to help improve AI and reduce bias by offering a formalized, interoperable, and transparent framework for organizing and interpreting knowledge. Using this method as it provides many benefits can help reduce bias, improve AI system accuracy, fairness and reliability.

Benefits of Ontology to AI:

- **Interpretability and explainability:** This method helps provide a transparent and interpretable representation of knowledge, that helps make it easier for humans to understand and interpret the decision making process of the AI system. As ontology method displays relationships and classes of data, it enables AI to provide better explanations for its decision and behaviour in a more transparent and interpretable manner, which in equivalent helps provide explainability for the AI, therefore the trustworthiness of the AI is increased and bias is reduced.
- **Formalized knowledge representation:** Ontology allows a more formalized framework for representing knowledge, allowing AI system to capture domain specific concepts, relationships, and constraints in a structured and consistent manner, encoding this method, AI systems can understand the semantics and context of the information provided in a better manner, which leads to a more reliable, accurate and relevant decision made by AI.

Frames

Frames are one of the simplest methods for knowledge representation, where data is stored as declarative facts organized in a structured way. Frames consist of slots that contain complex objects, broken down into frames and sub-slots. This approach helps structure and categorize data, representing classes, inheritance, and default values. By organizing entities such as race or other characteristics, frames provide a way for AI systems to manage and interpret data more effectively.

Benefits of Frames for AI:

- **Structured Representation:** Frames provide a structured approach for organizing data, enabling AI to capture relationships between entities, attributes, and contextual dependencies

more effectively. By encoding domain-specific knowledge in frames, AI systems can better understand and reason about data, leading to more accurate and contextually relevant outcomes.

- **Contextual Flexibility:** Frames offer flexibility by accommodating varying levels of detail and abstraction, allowing AI systems to adapt to different contexts. This flexibility helps AI handle uncertain or inconsistent data efficiently. By using contextual information, AI can make more informed decisions, which helps reduce bias and improve overall performance.
- **Bias Mitigation Strategies:** Frames can be used to encode bias mitigation strategies and fairness constraints directly within their structure. By including slots for demographic attributes, historical context, and ethical considerations, AI systems can integrate fairness-aware reasoning into their decision-making processes, promoting more equitable outcomes and reducing bias.
- **Transparency and Explainability:** Frames are inherently transparent, making it easier for humans to understand and interpret the data and decisions of AI systems. This transparency improves explainability, helping AI systems provide clearer justifications for their actions. By organizing data in a structured and understandable way, frames contribute to building trust in AI systems, reducing the risk of hidden biases or unfair outcomes.

Semantic Modelling

Semantic modelling enables AI systems to interpret and reason about information in a more contextually rich and nuanced manner by incorporating semantic annotations and metadata that reflect cultural, social, and linguistic dimensions. This method helps AI mitigate biases and align better with the needs of diverse users, improving aspects like interpretability, reasoning, and overall accuracy.

Benefits of Semantic Modelling for AI:

- **Interconnected View of Data:** Semantic modelling represents data as interconnected networks of concepts and semantic relationships. By capturing these associations, AI systems can understand contextual dependencies and infer implicit relationships between entities. This comprehensive view enables AI to make more informed and contextually relevant decisions, systematically reducing bias introduced by oversimplified or isolated data representations.
- **Contextual Understanding:** The semantic method provides AI with crucial context by making complex relationships and dependencies within the data more accessible and interpretable. By encoding semantic information, AI systems gain a deeper understanding of the underlying context and meaning, enabling them to make more trustworthy, reliable, accurate, and bias-free decisions.

3.2. Bias elimination techniques

As AI has been on the rise for several sectors, just like the benefits and advantages it has brought to multiple sectors, there are also challenges and limitations of AI, as bias has been a major problem for AI, with extreme and serious consequences, bias can be induced due to flawed design, biased data or even due to lack of diversity of developers or researchers. There has not been yet any concrete technical solutions to eliminate bias, however some researchers have been testing with various techniques.

Variable elimination

Some experts believe it is possible to remove bias by programming it out, a lot of experts believe removing some of the variables could help limit the bias for the AI, but in the process important data is removed. AFST(Allegheny Family Screening Tool)[14] is a healthcare AI algorithm that predicts if a child is living in an abusive environment and it takes into consideration variables such as child welfare, alcohol intake, living situation(housing), the data used is whatever public data is available about the family, however it was proved that this algorithm is human biased as it uses data of past calls about

domestic abuse which are normally involve dark-skinned people or biracial individuals, if multiple calls happen they are discarded which can cause algorithm not to be reliable and biased[15], this article suggests to perform an AI version of the “Blind taste test”, which involves removing key elements that identify the situation such as race, gender etc.... this expert suggests to deny the algorithm the information that is suspected of biasing the outcome(Blind testing).

However other researchers are trying to refute the technique of variable elimination, and they suggest that using this method for removing bias, limits the system and restricts from achieving fairness[16], and would be hard to control fairness. Some used variables could indirectly contribute to bias, when developer first glances at the data, it might not show any obvious bias, or might seem to have any effect of bias, but that what could be identified as hidden bias. The article suggests that performance metrics should be revised and developers need to manage their data better and have some strategies such as minimizing false positives, false negatives or impact check.

Removing certain sensitive variable does not necessarily mean or reflect that bias can be removed or reduced[17], as researchers in IBM argue that there is no consensus on how to measure fairness or what it represents, should fairness be measured by comparing the model’s accuracy with and without sensitive variables such as race or gender?, this article argues that previous works have been using simple examples and simulated data just for the sake of results and these data does not actually reflect the complexity of real-world. However if we try to remove certain variables, it is possible to reduce bias, reduce resource allocation or other impacts such as discrimination, however in the other hand the removal of certain variables could actually blind experts and ruin the performance of an AI model[18].

Correction of the Vector Space

Bias often emerges in the vector space where word embeddings are learned. Words associated with gender, ethnicity, or other sensitive attributes may perpetuate biases[19]. Correcting the vector space involves identifying dimensions harbouring bias and equalizing the distance between protected attributes (e.g., racial groups) and biased concepts (e.g., qualifications). This entails adjusting word pairs like “he” and “she” to ensure similar embeddings, thereby contributing to a more neutral representation of words. While this approach can mitigate stereotypes, it may cause semantic drift and fail to address intersectionality challenges.

Data Augmentation

Data augmentation is another effective technique for mitigating bias. It involves generating new data from existing training sets to diversify examples, exposing the model to a wider range of scenarios. This process begins with identifying underrepresented groups in the training data and modifying existing instances through techniques like synonym replacement or paraphrasing [20]. The goal is to balance the representation of protected attributes. However, data augmentation can also lead to overfitting, where the model becomes too tailored to augmented examples, potentially reducing its generalization ability.

3.3. Standards and recommendations

As Artificial intelligence has been widely used, it has made various fields easier, however as AI been enhancing sectors, it has also come with various challenges and other issues, which has risen the need of the regulations for AI especially in sensitive infrastructure[21],regulatory framework is very crucial and important for guiding the ethical development and deployment of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies. They help ensure that AI systems are designed, implemented, and used in ways that are fair, transparent, and accountable. Regulatory frameworks address key concerns such as bias, privacy, and security, and set standards for compliance that organizations must follow. They also foster public trust in AI by ensuring that AI technologies are developed with societal values and human rights in

mind. that is why sectors with critical infrastructure are still reluctant to implement AI in manager tasks in their structure, due to the lack of AI reliability and the relegation of it.

Numerous entities have putting a lot of efforts into regulating AI, one of the most notable being:

- **European Union AI Act[22]:** This comprehensive legislation categorises AI systems into four risk levels: unacceptable, high, limited, and minimal. It prohibits unacceptable-risk systems, such as government social scoring, while imposing strict requirements on high-risk applications like biometric identification and critical infrastructure. Developers must implement risk management protocols and maintain detailed documentation of their systems. Non-compliance can result in significant fines, reaching up to 6% of a company's global annual turnover, emphasising the serious repercussions of failing to adhere to the established regulations. The Act also supports startups and small-to-medium enterprises by providing testing environments before public deployment, although questions about metrics for assessing safety and transparency remain.
- **International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)[21]:** The IAEA aims to ensure the safe and ethical use of AI, particularly to prevent military applications. Its existing regulatory framework serves as a model for AI governance, offering a blueprint for developing standards that manage AI risks.
- **National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)[23]:** NIST has developed a risk management framework that promotes awareness of best practices for managing AI risks, providing guidance for developers and emphasising trustworthy and responsible AI use.
- **Consumer Technology Association (CTA)[24]:** The CTA has published guidelines for developing trustworthy AI software, focusing on accountability, data protection, and bias mitigation, which are crucial for protecting consumers in sensitive sectors.
- **ISO Standard[25]:** This standard addresses AI system transparency and explainability, emphasising trust through controllability and identifying engineering pitfalls. It provides approaches for assessing the reliability, accuracy, safety, and privacy of AI systems, making it applicable to sensitive infrastructure.
- **China's Regulatory Framework[26]:** This framework emphasises government-led initiatives and strong state control. Following the emergence of generative AI, China has introduced guidelines prioritising ethics, privacy, and national interests. China has been one of the first countries to ever release guidelines on generative AI after the release of Chatgpt[27], their regulatory framework for AI is characterised by strong state control and strategic emphasis on becoming a global leader in AI. Key aspects include:

The rapid integration of AI across sectors presents both opportunities and challenges, particularly in sensitive infrastructure. A robust regulatory framework is essential to ensure fair, transparent, and trustworthy AI systems. Efforts from entities such as the EU, IAEA, and NIST illustrate comprehensive approaches to managing AI risks. As AI continues to evolve, ongoing refinement of these frameworks is necessary to safeguard human rights and maximise the benefits of this transformative technology.

4. EVALUATION

4.1. Dataset

In this paper, the Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI)[27] Measures dataset was used to assess how using knowledge representation methods for the AI to better understand data can help enhance AI's predictive accuracy. The dataset consists of demographic and sensitive variables of 10,000 employees such as gender (male, female, non-binary), sexual orientation, race (e.g., Asian, Black, White), age, and job attributes like salary, job satisfaction (1-10 scale), department, and promotion rates. Reason for the specific choice of this dataset comes from fact, it helps improve diversity, equity and inclusion

in the workplace. Key correlations were established between job satisfaction, salary, and demographic groups using statistical tests.

One of the main focuses of this paper is to highlight the potential sources of bias and how these biases could influence the decision-making process of AI models. The choice of this dataset reflects the importance of understanding how sensitive attributes like gender, race, and sexual orientation can affect the accuracy and fairness of AI predictions.

Data Visualization and Feature Selection

The classifier used in our study relies primarily on categorical data, and for this reason, we emphasised the importance of these columns by eliminating numerical values (e.g., age and salary) from the feature matrix. A visualisation of some of the categorical columns is provided in Figure 1, with additional visualisations available in the code repository.

Figure 1. Data visualization

Data Preparation

The dataset has been divided between training and testing using **train_test_split** function. Feature Matrix and Target Vector Preparation:

- X: The feature matrix, which consists of: 'Division', 'Gender', 'Sexual_Orientation', 'LGBTQ', 'Ethnicity', 'Disability', 'Minority', 'Nationality'
- y: The target vector, which consists of the column 'Manager'. This is the variable we want to predict.

Train-Test Split:

- The function **train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)** splits the dataset into training and testing sets:
 - X_train, y_train: 80% of the data is assigned to the training set (since test_size=0.2, 20% is left for the test set).
 - X_test, y_test: 20% of the data is assigned to the test set

4.2. Methodology and evaluation

Classifier

The decision tree classifier was used in this paper in order to be able to predict whether an employee holds a manager position or not based on demographic and job related attributes.

Decision trees are non-parametric supervised learning methods that are widely used for both classification and regression tasks. The model splits the data into subsets based on the most informative features, with the aim of creating homogeneous groups where each group is dominated by one class. The decision tree was chosen for its simplicity and interpretability, which is crucial for understanding how sensitive attributes, such as gender and race, influence AI's predictions.

Evaluation metrics

As mentioned above, the dataset was divided into training and testing sets using an 80/20 split. The decision tree classifier was trained on the training dataset and its performance was evaluated using the test dataset, the classifier was evaluated by counting the accuracy and F1 score.

Accuracy:

Accuracy is a metric used to evaluate the performance of a classification model. It represents the proportion of correctly predicted instances (both true positives and true negatives) out of the total number of predictions. Accuracy is calculated as:

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The accuracy of the model has been calculated by comparing the predicted values of (y_{pred}) with the actual values of (y_{test}), as an output the classifier has showed an accuracy of 82.95%, which is still considered positive outcome, as it shows that the model could be considered reliable.

F1 score:

The F1 score is a performance metric used in classification tasks, especially when dealing with imbalanced datasets. It combines **precision** (the proportion of correctly predicted positive instances out of all predicted positives) and **recall** (the proportion of correctly predicted positive instances out of all actual positives) into a single score. The F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, calculated as:

$$F1\ Score = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (2)$$

Knowledge representation Method Implementation

The paper is exploring, the possibility of how knowledge representation methods, and using it for the AI to be able to understand the data in a more comprehensive manner, could lead to improving the accuracy of AI models.

After using the decision tree classifier, we have decided to implement two different knowledge representation methods, in order to explore the theory if the accuracy can be improved using knowledge representation, both semantic network and frame methods were implemented to explore if it can improve the accuracy, the results was compared against a baseline of the decision tree classifier, the accuracy displayed from the classifier and the ones from implementing both methods, was used to compare and evaluate, along with other metrics such as F1 score.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Baseline classifier performance

The baseline Decision Tree Classifier, trained on pre-processed data, achieved an accuracy of 82.95%, with an F1 score of 0.80. This indicates the model's ability to learn patterns from the data and make reasonably accurate predictions. However, the classifier's performance is limited to the information explicitly present in the training data.

5.2. Semantic Network Performance

The Semantic Network demonstrated an improvement over the baseline classifier, achieving an accuracy of 100% and an F1 score of 0.89. This highlights the system's ability to leverage its knowledge base to retrieve information not directly available in the training data. The structured representation of knowledge within the network enables efficient retrieval and reasoning. However, the Semantic Network's reliance on a predefined knowledge base can limit its adaptability to new information.

5.3. Frame-Based System Performance

The Frame-Based System further enhanced the performance, achieving an accuracy of 100% and an F1 score of 0.93. This system benefits from the flexibility of frames, allowing for representing complex relationships and constraints. The ability to store default values and procedural knowledge within frames improves the system's predictive capabilities. However, the design and maintenance of frames can be more complex compared to Semantic Networks.

5.4. Overall evaluation

Comparing the three systems, we observed a clear performance improvement with the integration of knowledge representation techniques. The Semantic Network and Frame-Based System outperformed the baseline classifier in terms of both accuracy and F1 score (see fig 2). This underscores the value of incorporating domain knowledge and structured representation for enhancing machine learning models. The Frame-Based System slightly outperformed the Semantic Network, indicating the potential benefits of its flexible and expressive representation capabilities.

Figure 2. F1 score evaluation

As the evaluation results shows that the implementation of knowledge representation methods, to help the artificial intelligence models better understand information and aid in improving prediction, has been shown to be effective (see table 1). The knowledge-based systems provide a mechanism to leverage domain knowledge and reasoning, enabling predictions beyond the limitations of the training data. However, the complexity of designing and maintaining knowledge bases should be considered.

Table 1. Comparative analysis

System	Accuracy(%)	F1 score
Baseline	0.83	0.80
Semantic Network	100	0.89
Frame-Based system	100	0.93

6. LIMITATIONS

The reported results and the evaluation of the accuracy are based on the specific dataset we have used, as future work we are planning to explore how results can vary with different datasets and knowledge representations methods.

As the reported accuracy and F1 score, shows a lot of promise how knowledge representation can aid improve the decision-making and prediction process for AI models, however there might be multiple limitations to be considered.

- **Dataset Scope:** The dataset used for evaluation may not fully represent the complexity and diversity of real-world scenarios. Further evaluation on larger and more diverse datasets is necessary to validate the system's generalizability.
- **Knowledge Base Design:** The knowledge base used in this study was manually crafted and may not be exhaustive or perfectly accurate. Automating knowledge base construction and incorporating external knowledge sources could address this limitation.
- **Computational Complexity:** The knowledge representation systems, especially the Frame-Based System, can introduce computational overhead compared to a standalone classifier. This should be considered when deploying the system in real-time applications.
- **Maintainability:** As the knowledge base grows, maintaining its consistency and accuracy becomes crucial. Implementing efficient knowledge base management strategies is essential for long-term system usability.
- **Interpretability:** While knowledge representation can improve prediction accuracy, it can also make the system less transparent. Further research is needed to develop methods for explaining the system's reasoning and predictions.

7. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the exploration of bias in AI and its impacts, and how it can be mitigated is actually a very complex landscape that should be explored more in detail, before suggesting possible solutions, bias in AI must be explored in a more historical aspect. Multiple techniques exist that can help reduce bias in AI, such as variable extraction, can offer promising aspect into removing bias by addressing

sensitive attributes, however some studies suggest that such techniques diminish the performance of AI.

One of the most promising is knowledge representation as it can be used to proof, that in fact the way the AI learns, its output is affected, the different knowledge representation techniques discussed previously show that if AI can learn using different techniques, it would help eliminate a bit of bias and improve its output.

Knowledge representation can play a pivotal role into encoding data in a more meaningful manner that allows the AI system to better understand it, the mentioned techniques such as semantic networks or ontologies can enable AI to capture the complex relationship and contextual information, which enhances and ensures accuracy and fairness of AI decisions. Incorporating diverse perspectives and ensuring representational diversity within AI models can mitigate biases rooted in dataset.

The paper demonstrated the potential of integrating knowledge representation techniques with machine learning for enhanced information retrieval and prediction in the context of employee data analysis. Both the Semantic Network and Frame-Based System outperformed the baseline Decision Tree Classifier, achieving higher accuracy and F1 scores. This highlights the value of incorporating domain knowledge and structured representations for improving prediction capabilities. While the Frame-Based System exhibited a slight advantage in performance, the choice between the two knowledge representation approaches depends on the specific application and data characteristics.

8. FUTURE WORK

Future work could explore more complex knowledge representation techniques, such as ontologies or logics, to further enhance the system's reasoning capabilities. Incorporating external knowledge sources and developing automated knowledge base construction methods could also improve the system's adaptability and scalability. Additionally, integrating Explainable AI techniques like LIME and SHAP with knowledge-based approaches could provide deeper insights into model decisions, promoting greater trustworthiness. Further efforts may also focus on addressing identified limitations, such as dataset scope and knowledge base design, to improve the system's robustness and generalizability. Overall, this paper contributes to advancing knowledge-based machine learning systems and their potential applications across various domains.

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